

Patterns and Impact of Foot Injuries: An Observational Study at Hamidia Hospital

Rahul Rohila^{1*}, Suresh Uikey², Saurabh Cholkar¹, Vinod Rawat¹

¹MS Orthopaedics, PG Resident, Department of Orthopaedics, Gandhi Medical College & Associated Hamidia Hospital, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh, India

² MS Orthopaedics, Associate Professor, Department of Orthopaedics, Gandhi Medical College & Associated Hamidia Hospital, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Rahul Rohila

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Abstract:

Background: Foot injuries are prevalent among active individuals, often leading to significant functional impairments. These injuries, although rarely life-threatening, require proper management to prevent long-term complications and disability.

Aim and Objective: To investigate the patterns of foot injuries among patients presenting at Hamidia Hospital, Bhopal.

Materials and Methods: This observational study was conducted from January 2021 to June 2022 in the Department of Orthopaedics at Gandhi Medical College, Bhopal. Patients of all ages and both genders presenting with foot injuries and who consented to participate were included. Data were collected through patient interviews, physical examinations, and medical record reviews, including demographic details, mode of injury, type of injury, location, side of injury, and severity. Radiographic assessments confirmed the presence and type of fractures and dislocations. Descriptive statistics were used to analyze the data.

Results: The study included 955 patients, with a mean age of 34.97 years. The majority of patients were young adults, with the highest incidence in the 21-30 age group (24.5%), followed by the 31-40 age group (23.4%). A higher incidence was observed in males (76.6%) compared to females (23.4%). Road traffic accidents were the leading cause of foot injuries (68.8%), followed by falls from height (13.4%) and slips and falls (9.1%). Most injuries involved a single region (92.1%), with the forefoot being the most commonly affected region (55.22%). Bilateral injuries occurred in 7.64% of cases. Associated injuries were present in 46.0% of patients, and 61.6% of injuries were open. Foot fractures without dislocations were observed in 91.62% of cases, with the remaining 8.38% having single or multiple dislocations.

Conclusion: Foot injuries predominantly affect young and middle-aged males, with road traffic accidents being the primary cause. Most injuries involved the forefoot and were often isolated. The high prevalence of associated and open injuries highlights the need for enhanced traffic and workplace safety measures, public awareness campaigns, and prompt medical intervention to reduce the incidence and severity of foot injuries and improve patient outcomes.

Keywords: Foot Injuries, Road Traffic Accidents, Epidemiology, Trauma, Orthopaedic Management.

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Introduction

Foot injuries are prevalent among athletes and physically active individuals, significantly impacting their ability to participate in sports and other activities. [1] These injuries, although rarely life-threatening, can lead to substantial functional impairments if not correctly managed. [2] The foot serves as the base of the lower kinetic chain, and improper rehabilitation of foot injuries can result in secondary complications higher up the kinetic chain. [3]

Each year, a significant number of individuals present to accident and emergency departments with acute ankle sprains. [4] Lateral ligament

injuries account for the majority of these sprains. Despite many patients undergoing radiographic assessments, a significant proportion do not have fractures. [5] Guidelines, such as the Ottawa foot rules, have been established to rationalize using radiography to assess these injuries, achieving high sensitivity for detecting fractures. Accurate palpation of landmarks such as the lateral and medial malleoli is crucial to avoid underestimating or missing injuries. [5, 6]

Foot injuries are also common among endurance runners, with a high incidence rate annually. These injuries represent a substantial portion of all

injuries in this population. Proper evaluation and management of these injuries are essential to avoid chronic pain, recurrent instability, and other complications. [7]

Recent interest in the subspecialty of foot has led to an increase in focused research, conferences, and publications. Studies have shown that foot injuries are common in athletic activities and occur across all age brackets. In our research, we aim to observe the patterns of foot injuries among patients presenting at Hamidia Hospital. By understanding these patterns, we hope to contribute to better diagnosis, management, and prevention strategies for foot injuries.

Materials and Methods

This observational study investigated the patterns of foot injuries among patients presenting at Hamidia Hospital from January 2021 to June 2022. The research was carried out in the Department of Orthopaedics at Gandhi Medical College, Bhopal. The hospital provides medical care to a large population, ensuring a diverse sample of foot injury cases.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients presenting with foot injuries.
- Both genders and all age groups were included.
- Patients who consented to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with pre-existing foot deformities or chronic conditions affecting the foot.
- Patients who did not consent to participate.
- Patients with incomplete medical records.

Through patient interviews, physical examinations, and medical record reviews. The following information was recorded:

- Demographic details: age, gender, occupation.
- Mode of injury: road traffic accidents, falls, sports injuries, and other causes.
- Type of injury: fractures, dislocations, sprains, and associated injuries.
- Location of injury: forefoot, midfoot, hindfoot, or multiple regions.
- Side of injury: left, right, or bilateral.
- The severity of injury: classified using the Foot and Ankle Severity Scale (FASS).

Diagnostic Methods

- Radiographic assessments were performed on all patients to confirm the presence and type of fractures and dislocations.
- Clinical examinations included palpation, range of motion tests, and special tests to assess ligamentous injuries and tendon integrity.

Statistical Analysis

The collected data was analyzed using descriptive statistics. Tables and graphs presented the distribution of cases according to age, gender, mode of trauma, type and location of injury, and severity.

Ethical Considerations

The study protocol was reviewed and approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee of Gandhi Medical College, Bhopal. Informed consent was obtained from all participants before their inclusion in the study. Patient confidentiality was maintained throughout the research process.

Results

Table 1: Characteristics of the study population

Variables	Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Age Group	<20	200	20.9%
	21-30	234	24.5%
	31-40	223	23.4%
	41-50	137	14.3%
	51-60	92	9.6%
	61-70	59	6.2%
	71-80	9	0.9%
	>80	1	0.1%
Mean age	34.97±15.963		
Sex	Male	732	76.6%
	Female	223	23.4%
Mode of Trauma	Assault	48	5.0
	Fall From height	128	13.4
	Fall of a heavy object	35	3.7
	RTA	657	68.8
	Slip and fall	87	9.1
Number of regions of foot injury	Multiple regions involved	75	7.9%
	Single (Isolated regions injury)	880	92.1%

Region of Foot	Forefoot	604	55.22%
	Midfoot	115	09.59%
	Hindfoot	385	35.19%
Multiple Regions of Foot	Multiple F/H	49	65.3%
	Multiple F/M	23	30.7%
	Multiple F/M/H	1	1.3%
	Multiple M/H	2	2.7%
Side	Left	432	45.23%
	Right	450	47.13%
	Bilateral	73	7.64%
Associated Injury	Yes	439	46.0%
	No	516	54.0%
Type of injury	Closed	367	38.4
	Open	588	61.6

The study population primarily consisted of young adults and middle-aged individuals, with the majority of patients falling within the 21-30 age group (24.5%), followed closely by the 31-40 age group (23.4%). The mean age of the patients was approximately 35 years, indicating that foot injuries were more prevalent among this demographic.

A significantly higher number of males (76.6%) than females (23.4%) presented with foot injuries. This suggests that males were more prone to activities or circumstances leading to such injuries.

The leading cause of foot injuries was road traffic accidents (RTA), accounting for 68.8% of cases. Other notable causes included falls from height (13.4%) and slips and falls (9.1%).

Most foot injuries involved a single region (92.1%), while 7.9% involved multiple areas. Among the specific regions of the foot affected, forefoot injuries were the most common (55.22%), followed by hindfoot injuries (35.19%) and midfoot injuries (9.59%).

Multiple region injuries predominantly involved the forefoot and hindfoot (65.3%), with less frequent combinations including the forefoot and midfoot (30.7%), and rare cases involving all three regions or the midfoot and hindfoot.

The distribution of injuries according to the side of the foot showed a nearly even split between left foot injuries (45.23%) and right foot injuries (47.13%), with bilateral injuries occurring in 7.64% of the cases.

46.0% of the patients had associated injuries, while 54.0% had isolated foot injuries. The majority of the injuries were open (61.6%), with closed injuries accounting for 38.4%.

Out of 955 patients, 875 (91.62%) patients had foot fractures that were not associated with any dislocation in the foot. Rest 80 (8.38%) had single or multiple dislocations.

Table 2: Distribution of Cases according to Type of Dislocation

Dislocation Type	No. of Cases	Percentage
CHOPART	15	17.29
DIP	3	3.45
HEEL PAD AVULSION	12	13.79
LISFRANC	28	33.23
MTP	10	11.54
PIP	1	.01
SUBTALAR	18	20.68
Total	87	100.0

In all the 955 patients with unilateral or bilateral foot involvement, with the involved foot getting injuries in multiple or single regions, we found the total no. of injuries to be 1122.

Of 1122 bone injuries, the forefoot had 621 (55.35%) bones injured, the most common region of the foot getting fractured in the foot. In the forefoot, metatarsal is the most common bone to be fractured, with no. of 494(79.55%) among forefoot

fractures, followed by phalanges fractures 127 (20.45%).

The midfoot had 116 (10.34%) fractured bones. It is the least commonly injured region of the foot. Navicular bones are the most common bone injury in midfoot, with 86.21% (100 cases)

The hindfoot involved 385 (34.31%) bone injuries, with the calcaneum being most commonly

fractured at 340 (88.31%). The remaining 45 (11.69%) bone injuries were in the talus bone.

The metatarsal is the most common bone in the foot to be injured, with 44.03% of cases. Calcaneal fractures with a percentage of 30.30 follow it.

Phalangeal and navicular fractures were present in 11.32% of cases and 8.91%, respectively. Cuneiform was reported to be the least common bone injury in all feet, with 7 cases (0.63%), sitting close with 9 cuboid fracture cases (0.80%).

All bilateral open wounds, associated joint dislocations, and injuries in more than one region of the foot were termed severe foot injuries. In our study, we found that 669 cases (70.09%) had severe foot injuries (Figure 1).

Discussion

The foot is a terminal and principal part of the body's weight-bearing or transferring chain. Foot trauma can be a significant cause of morbidity not only to the foot but can also affect all the parts of the chain. Foot injuries can be a significant cause of morbidity and sometimes mortality.

The study demonstrated a significant prevalence of foot injuries among young and middle-aged adults, with the highest incidence observed in the 21-30 age group (24.5%), followed closely by the 31-40 age group (23.4%). Oleske et al. [8] studied a total of 990 work-related injuries to the foot of employees from private-sector companies. The mean age of the worker with a foot injury was 34.2 years (± 12.0). According to Jeffers et al. [9], the parent population of 1239 contained 53 (4.3%) foot-injured motorcyclists (49 men) with a mean age of 31.7 years (range 18-79 years). The mean age of 34.97 years further supports the notion that foot injuries are predominantly an issue for younger, active individuals.

A pronounced male predominance was observed, with 76.6% of the cases involving males. This disparity could be attributed to higher engagement

in high-risk activities and occupations among males. It is well backed by the literature we have on the epidemiology of foot injury. In an article by Ayman M A Tadros et al. [10], gender incidence of foot injuries in previous studies varied from 50% males in the general population to 92% males amongst motorcyclists. A survey by Dhillon et al. [11] suggests that around 82% of cases were males. Road traffic accidents (RTA) emerged as the leading cause of foot injuries, accounting for 68.8% of cases. This pattern is well supported by studies done previously by Sharma et al. [12] and in the study by Dhillon et al. [11], where they found road traffic accidents as the most common mode of trauma. This further catches the fact that poor road facilities and driving skills in developing countries could be a cause for RTA to be the most common mode of trauma in the population of developing countries like India. Falls from height and slips and falls were other significant causes, contributing 13.4% and 9.1% of the cases, respectively. These findings highlight the need for improved safety measures in both traffic and occupational settings to reduce the incidence of such injuries.

The majority of the injuries involved a single region of the foot (92.1%), with forefoot injuries being the most common (55.22%). A study by Dhillon et al [11] where found 8.21% of cases with bilateral foot fractures. Left-sided injuries were 32.84%, and 58.94% were right-sided cases. Another study by Tadros et al. [10] recorded 95 right-sided, 66 left-sided, and 10 bilateral foot

injuries. Hindfoot injuries accounted for 35.19% of cases, while midfoot injuries were less common at 9.59%.

Multiple region injuries were predominantly found in the forefoot and hindfoot (65.3%), with a smaller percentage involving the forefoot and midfoot (30.7%). Bilateral injuries were relatively rare, occurring in 7.64% of the cases. This pattern of injury distribution suggests that certain activities and trauma mechanisms predominantly affect specific regions of the foot. A study done by Dhillon et al [11] says (most commonly) 53.1% of the forefoot, 33.9% percent of the hind foot, and 13% percent midfoot is the least common injured region of the foot.

Associated injuries were present in 46.0% of the patients, indicating a significant occurrence of concurrent trauma. The high percentage of open injuries (61.6%) versus closed injuries (38.4%) underscores the severity of the incidents leading to foot injuries and the need for immediate and comprehensive medical intervention to prevent complications such as infections and long-term disability. Enough of literature supports this finding that the lower limb is the most common trauma associated with foot injuries. Dhillon et al. [11] studied that about 47.01% of foot injuries were polytrauma cases. The lower limb was the most common, with 34.33%, followed by the upper limb at 13%. Atkins et al. ¹³ had 22% associated injury in their study, which may be accounted for by the fact that it was a study specifically on calcaneum bone.

The presence of foot fractures without associated dislocations in 91.62% of cases suggests that while fractures are common, dislocations are less frequent. This may reflect the nature of the trauma and the anatomical resilience of certain foot joints. As a rule, any dislocation should be taken with serious care and swift intervention. However, these injuries are frequently missed in emergencies, the reasons for which are multifactorial. Every midfoot closed swelling should be checked with eagle eyes, and any suspicious clinical finding should be confirmed radiologically. Early diagnosis can lead to early treatment and fewer deformities and morbidities in patients.

As described in the methodology, all bilateral injuries, injuries in multiple regions of a foot, open injuries, and open injuries are labeled severe foot injuries, advocating fast and careful management; the literature, too, points in the same direction of the pattern. Studies done in India by Sharma et al. ¹² and Dhillon et al. [11] had 72.8% and 41.79% of severe foot injuries, respectively. A study done in UAE by Tadros et al. [10] found that 41 % of injuries were severe foot injuries.

Overall, this study's findings emphasize the critical need for targeted prevention strategies, particularly addressing the high incidence of RTAs and the significant number of foot injuries among young adults and males. Enhanced safety protocols in traffic and workplaces and public awareness campaigns could reduce the burden of foot injuries. Additionally, timely and effective medical management is crucial to mitigate the impact of severe and open injuries on patients' long-term health and functionality.

Conclusion

This study highlights the significant burden of foot injuries among young and middle-aged adults, with a mean age of approximately 35 years and a higher prevalence in males. Road traffic accidents were the leading cause, followed by falls from height and slips. Most injuries involved a single region, particularly the forefoot, while multiple region injuries often included the forefoot and hindfoot. Nearly half of the patients had associated injuries, and open injuries were prevalent, indicating severe trauma. These findings underscore the need for enhanced traffic and workplace safety measures, public awareness campaigns, and prompt medical intervention to reduce the incidence and severity of foot injuries and improve patient outcomes.

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